

Supporting information

Electroactive covalent linkers for enhancing conducting polymer adhesion, charge transfer, and biological integration of PEDOT-coated carbon microfibers

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Experimental section – Synthesis of EDOT derivatives

Synthesis of EDOT-Ph-NO₂^[1]

To a solution of 3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene-2-boronic acid pinacol ester (400 mg, 1.5 mmol) in DMF (30 mL) were added 371 mg (1.5 mmol) of 1-iodo-4-nitrobenzene and 477 mg (3 mmol) of Na₂CO₃. The resulting mixture was bubbled with argon for 10 minutes and then tetrakis(triphenylphosphine)-palladium(0) (86 mg, 5 mol%) was added. The reaction was stirred under argon atmosphere for 48 h at 110°C and allowed to reach room temperature. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure, the crude residue was dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ and washed with water (x3), and the organic layer was dried over anhydrous MgSO₄ and filtered. The crude product was finally purified by column chromatography (hexane:dichloromethane = 1:1) to yield 310 mg of pure EDOT-Ph-NO₂ (Yield = 79%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.23 (d, *J* = 7.03 Hz, 2H), 7.88 (d, *J* = 9.16 Hz, 2H), 6.49 (s, 1H), 4.48 – 4.37 (m, 4H), 4.34 – 4.27 (m, 4H).

Synthesis of EDOT-Ph-NH₂^[1]

A solution of EDOT-Ph-NO₂ (200 mg, 0.76 mmol) in 30 mL of EtOH was prepared and bubbled with argon for 10 minutes. Then SnCl₂·2H₂O (1.03 gr, 4.56 mmol) was added and the mixture heated at 80°C for 24 h. After removal of most of the EtOH under reduced pressure, saturated aq. NaOH solution was added dropwise to the reaction mixture with stirring until the mixture became slightly basic. The product was extracted with ethyl acetate. The organic layer was dried over anhydrous MgSO₄ and filtered. The crude product was finally purified by column chromatography (ethyl acetate:hexane = 3:7) to yield 120 mg of pure EDOT-Ph-NH₂ (Yield = 67%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.54 (d, *J* = 6.87 Hz, 2H), 6.71 (d, *J* = 8.56 Hz, 2H), 6.23 (s, 1H), 4.26 (d, *J* = 15.77 Hz, 4H), 3.64 (s, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 145.35, 142.23, 136.74, 127.36, 123.69, 118.08, 115.22, 95.69, 77.53, 77.21, 76.89, 64.72, 64.56.

Synthesis of TPA-NO₂^[2]

To a stirring solution of diphenylamine (2 g, 11.82 mmol) in DMSO (100 mL) were added 1-iodo-4-nitrobenzene (4.41 g, 17.73 mmol) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (2.45 g, 17.73 mmol). The resulting mixture was bubbled with argon for 10 minutes and then palladium (II) acetate (79.6 mg, 3 mol%) was added. The reaction was stirred

under argon atmosphere for 24 h and quenched with a saturated ammonium chloride solution. The residue was extracted with ethyl acetate and washed with brine and water, and the organic layer was dried over anhydrous MgSO_4 and filtered. The crude product was finally purified by column chromatography (hexane:ethyl acetate = 95:5) to yield 3 gr of pure TPA- NO_2 (Yield = 87%). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.06 (d, J = 9.29 Hz, 2H), 7.44 – 7.34 (m, 4H), 7.27 – 7.17 (m, 6H), 6.95 (d, J = 9.29 Hz, 2H).

Synthesis of TPA- NO_2Br_2 ^[2]

A mixture of 4-nitrotriphenylamine (1 g, 3.4 mmol) and N-Bromosuccinimide (NBS, 1.5 g, 8.6 mmol) was stirred in anhydrous dimethylformamide (20 mL) at 0 °C until the completion of the reaction as monitored by TLC (24 h). Upon completion the reaction mixture was quenched with 30 mL of ice-water and extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (3 x 20 mL), and the organic layer was dried over anhydrous MgSO_4 and filtered. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure to afford 850 mg of TPA- NO_2Br_2 that was used without further purification (Yield = 57%). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.09 (d, J = 9.41 Hz, 2H), 7.50 (d, J = 9.54 Hz, 4H), 7.05 (d, J = 10.15 Hz, 4H), 6.99 (d, J = 8.80 Hz, 2H).

Synthesis of EDOT₂-TPA- NO_2 ^[2]

A mixture of bis(4-bromophenyl) (4'-nitrophenyl)amine (900 mg, 2 mmol) and tributyl(2,3-dihydrothieno[3,4-b][1,4]dioxin-5-yl)stannate (866 mg, 6 mmol) in DMF (30 mL) was bubbled with argon for 10 minutes and then tetrakis(triphenylphosphine)-palladium(0) (115.6 mg, 5 mol%) was added. After vigorously stirring at 110 °C under argon atmosphere for 18 h, the reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The resulting oily product was dissolved in ethyl acetate (30 mL) and washed with a saturated solution of NaHCO_3 (2 x 20 mL) and then brine (2 x 20 mL) and water (2 x 20 mL). The crude product was finally purified by flash column chromatography on silica gel (toluene:hexane = 1:20 to 1:10) to yield 340 mg of pure TPA- NO_2Edot_2 (Yield = 28%). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.09 (d, J = 9.41 Hz, 2H), 7.54 (d, J = 8.80 Hz, 2H), 7.17 (d, J = 9.67 Hz, 2H), 6.99 (d, J = 9.66 Hz, 2H), 4.41 – 4.28 (m, 8H).

Synthesis of EDOT₂-TPA- NH_2

A solution of EDOT₂-TPA-NO₂ (100 mg, 0.17 mmol) in EtOH (20 mL) was bubbled with argon for 10 minutes and then anhydrous tin chloride (SnCl₂, 200 mg, 1.05 mmol) was added and the reaction was stirred at 80 °C under argon atmosphere for 16 h. After removal of most of the EtOH under reduced pressure, to the reaction mixture was added saturated aq. NaOH solution dropwise with stirring until the mixture became slightly basic. The product was extracted with ethyl acetate. The organic layer was dried over anhydrous MgSO₄ and filtered. The crude product was finally purified by column chromatography in toluene to yield 57 mg of pure EDOT₂-TPA-NO₂ (Yield = 60%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.55 (d, *J* = 8.12 Hz, 4H), 7.19 – 6.88 (m, 6H), 6.67 (d, *J* = 7.98 Hz, 2H), 6.25 (d, *J* = 2.77 Hz, 2H), 4.43 – 4.14 (m, 8H), 3.69 (s, 4H).

Synthesis of EDOT-Ph-N₃

Edot-Ph-NH₂ (60 mg, 0,26 mmol) was dissolved in a mixture of water/acetic acid (1:2) and the mixture was cooled to 0°C. Then 25 mg (0.36 mmol) of NaNO₂ in water (2 ml) were added dropwise into the reaction mixture and the reaction was stirred at 0 °C for 1 hour. Next, NaN₃ (25.3 mg, 0.39 mmol) was added slowly, and the mixture was warmed to room temperature and stirred for two additional hours. The mixture was extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 x 20 mL). The organic layer was washed with saturated aqueous NaHCO₃ (3 x 20 mL), brine (20 mL), and water. The organic layer was dried over anhydrous MgSO₄ and filtered, and the solvents were concentrated under reduced pressure to afford 52 mg of pure Edot-Ph-N₃ that was used without further purification (Yield = 78%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.73 (d, *J* = 11.49 Hz, 2H), 7.04 (d, *J* = 8.68 Hz, 2H), 6.32 (s, 1H), 4.63 – 4.05 (m, 4H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 142.33, 138.23, 137.86, 130.20, 127.26, 119.24, 116.58, 97.58, 77.62, 77.30, 76.98, 64.81, 64.44. ATR-FTIR: ν = 2120 cm⁻¹ (-N=N=N).

[1] G. Trippé-Allardet *al.* Tetrahedron 69 (2013) 861–866.

[2] S. Li, et al. Polymers (Basel) 9 (2017)173

Scheme S1.(a) and (b) Synthetic pathways for the preparation of the amino derivatives EDOT-Ph-NH₂ and EDOT₂-TPA-NH₂, and (c) synthetic pathway for the preparation of the azido derivative EDOT-Ph-N₃.

Figure S1. ¹H NMR spectra (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for: a) EDOT-Ph-NH₂ and b) EDOT-Ph-N₃.

Figure S2. ^{13}C NMR spectra (100 MHz, CDCl_3) for a) EDOT-Ph-NH₂ and b) EDOT-Ph-N₃.

Figure S3. ¹H NMR spectra (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for: a) EDOT₂-TPA-NO₂, and b) EDOT₂-TPA-NH₂.

Figure S4. Mass spectra for: a) EDOT-Ph-NH₂, b) EDOT-Ph-N₃, and c) EDOT₂-TPA-NH₂. The inset in Figure b shows the FTIR spectrum of EDOT-Ph-N₃ highlighting the presence of the azide group.

Figure S5. XPS survey spectra of the EDOT derivatives at the top of each figure: a) EDOT-Ph-NH₂, b) EDOT-Ph-N₃, and c) EDOT₂-TPA-NH₂. Below the comparison of the N 1s high resolution spectra of the EDOT derivatives and their corresponding functionalized materials (*f*-CMF 1-3) is presented.

Table S1. Atomic percentages for starting CMFs and functionalized materials determined from XPS Analysis.

Samples	C1s (%)	O1s (%)	N1s (%)	S2p (%)	Si2p (%)
StartingCMFs	82.94	11.03	4.51		1.52
Edot-Ph-NH₂	72.62	18.02	0.64	0.71	8.01
<i>f</i>-CMF 1	76.57	17.00	4.31	1.37	0.75
EDOT₂-TPA-NH₂	70.38	17.35	3.27	3.19	5.81
<i>f</i>-CMF 2	79.88	13.26	4.98	1.51	0.38
Edot-Ph-N₃	67.21	18.18	4.17	2.52	7.92
<i>f</i>-CMF 3	84.34	9.96	4.53	0.94	0.23

Figure S6. Current transients obtained during chronoamperometric tests by application of a 0.3 V pulse train to the different electrodes. Responses from the 3rd and 4th pulses of ten-pulse trains are shown. a) Comparison of *f*-CMF 1 electrodes vs. starting CMF electrodes, before and after PEDOT:PSS-co-MA polymer electrodeposition. b) As a), but with *f*-CMF 2 electrodes. c) As a), but with *f*-CMF 3 electrodes. d) Washed *f*-CMF 3 electrodes vs. washed starting CMF electrodes, before and after polymer electrodeposition.

Figure S7. a,b) Impedance phase angle plotted as a function of frequency, analyzed at the indicated times of mechanical stress (vibration) for starting PCMFs (a) and PEDOT-coated *f*-CMFs 3 (b). c) Comparison of phase angle data from starting PCMFs and PEDOT-coated *f*-CMFs 3 at 0, 2 and 10 min of vibration. All data are expressed as mean \pm standard errors.

Figure S8. Immunohistochemical characterization of cellular reactions to control (non-functionalized, washed PCMFs) and aziridine-functionalized PCMFs (i.e., *f*-PCMFs 3) at one-month post implantation in the rat spinal cord. Horizontal, 10- μ m horizontal spinal cord sections were immunostained for the indicated cellular markers and the fluorescent images were merged with bright-field photographs for simultaneous visualization of the MFs. Scale bar, 50- μ m. Arrow heads signal the cut microfibers. Isolectin GS-IB₄ (IB4, Alexa Fluor™ 488 Conjugate, Invitrogen, I21411) was used to identify macrophages, endothelial cells, and microglia. ED1 staining (Chemicon MAB1435, 1:250) labelled macrophages and activated microglia. Reactivity for platelet-derived growth factor receptor (PDGFR, Abcam AB32570, 1:100) revealed fibroblasts and pericytes. Glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP, BD Biosciences 556327, 1:500) labelled astrocytes. In addition, cell nuclei were stained with Hoechst 33342 (Molecular Probes, 1.5 mg/ml in PBS applied for 15 min). Secondary IgG antibodies labeled with Alexa-488 or Alexa-594 (Molecular Probes) were used. Controls without the primary antibodies were included in all procedures to verify the reliability of the labeling.